

1 Cross-mapping of terms used in chemical risk assessment with 2 those used in systematic review: research protocol

3 Camilla Svendsen^{1,2†}, Gro H. Mathisen¹, Gunn E. Vist^{1,3}, Trine Husøy^{1,4}, Heather M. Ames^{1,3},
4 Anna Beronius⁵, Emma Di Consiglio⁶, Ingrid Druwe⁷, Thomas Hartung^{8,9}, Sebastian
5 Hoffmann^{10,11}, Carlijn R. Hooijmans¹², Kyriaki Machera¹³, Joshua F. Robinson¹⁴, Erwin
6 Roggen¹⁵, Andrew A. Rooney¹⁶, Nicolas Roth^{17,18}, Eliana Spilioti¹³, Anastasia Spyropoulou¹³,
7 Olga Tcheremenskaia⁶, Emanuela Testai⁶, Mathieu Vinken¹⁹, Paul Whaley^{1,20†}

8 ¹Norwegian Scientific Committee for Food and Environment, Norwegian Institute of Public
9 Health, Oslo, Norway

10 ²Department of Chemical Toxicology, Norwegian Institute of Public Health, Oslo, Norway

11 ³Division for Health Services, Norwegian Institute of Public Health, Oslo, Norway

12 ⁴Department of Food Safety, Norwegian Institute of Public Health, Oslo, Norway

13 ⁵Institute of Environmental Medicine, Karolinska Institutet, Stockholm, Sweden

14 ⁶Environment & Health Department, Italian National Institute of Health (ISS), Rome, Italy

15 ⁷United States Environmental Protection Agency, Office of Research and Development,
16 Center for Public Health and Environmental Assessments, Research Triangle Park, NC,
17 USA.

18 ⁸Center for Alternatives to Animal Testing (CAAT), Johns Hopkins University, Bloomberg
19 School of Public Health, Baltimore, MD, USA

20 ⁹CAAT Europe, University of Konstanz, Konstanz, Germany

21 ¹⁰Evidence-based toxicology collaboration (EBTC), Johns Hopkins University, Bloomberg
22 School of Public Health, Baltimore, MD, USA

23 ¹¹seh consulting + services, Paderborn, Germany

24 ¹²Department of Anesthesiology, Pain and Palliative Care, Radboud University Medical
25 Centre, Nijmegen, Netherlands

26 ¹³Laboratory of Toxicological Control of Pesticides, Scientific Directorate of Pesticides'
27 Control and Phytopharmacy, Benaki Phytopathological Institute, Kifissia, Greece

28 ¹⁴Department of Obstetrics, Gynecology & Reproductive Sciences, University of California,
29 San Francisco (UCSF), USA

30 ¹⁵3Rs Management and Consulting ApS, Lyngby, Denmark

31 ¹⁶Division of Translational Toxicology, National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences,
32 Research Triangle Park, NC, USA

33 ¹⁷Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences, University of Basel, Basel, Switzerland

34 ¹⁸Swiss Centre for Applied Human Toxicology (SCAHT), University of Basel, Basel,
35 Switzerland

36 ¹⁹Department of Pharmaceutical and Pharmacological Sciences, Vrije Universiteit Brussel;
37 Belgium

38 ²⁰Lancaster Environment Centre, Lancaster University, Lancaster, UK

39 †Correspondence should be addressed to Camilla Svendsen; E-mail:
40 camilla.svendsen@fhi.no and Paul Whaley; E-mail: paul@whaleyresearch.uk.

41 Disclaimer

42 The author Ingrid Druwe is employed at the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency. The
43 views expressed in this manuscript are those of the authors and do not necessarily
44 represent the views or policies of the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency.

45 The author Andrew A. Rooney is employed at the U.S. National Institute of Environmental
46 Health Sciences. The views expressed in this manuscript are those of the authors and do
47 not necessarily represent the views or policies of the U.S. National Institute of Environmental
48 Health Sciences.

49 Abstract

50 The focus on implementation of systematic review (SR) principles in chemical risk
51 assessments (CRAs) is growing as it has the potential to advance the rigour and
52 transparency of the CRAs. However, the SR and CRA communities use their own specific
53 terminologies. Understanding the meaning of core SR and CRA terms and where they
54 overlap is critical for application of SR methods and principles in CRAs. Moreover, it will
55 increase the possibility for cross-sectorial collaboration, avoid misunderstandings, and
56 improve communication among risk assessors, researchers, and policy makers.

57 We present a process for the cross-mapping of core CRA terms and core SR terms. Core
58 terms for study appraisal, evidence synthesis and integration used in the SR and CRA
59 communities will be included. The outcome will be an overview of how core SR terms map

60 onto core CRA terms and vice versa, and a description of the relationship and conceptual
61 overlap between the terms.

62 The cross-mapping is divided in three phases, where in the first phase the core SR and CRA
63 terms will be identified. In the second phase, existing SR and CRA definitions will be
64 mapped. In the third phase, descriptions of the relationship and conceptual overlap between
65 the terms will be derived. The third phase will include weekly one-hour online meetings for
66 SR and CRA experts.

67 Key words

68 Conceptual overlap, cross-mapping, definitions, interoperability, terminology.

69 1. Introduction

70 Chemical risk assessments (CRAs) should be evidence-based, which means that they are
71 grounded in a comprehensive and rigorous, transparent and objective analysis of all
72 evidence relating to the assessment task. Applying systematic review (SR) principles in
73 CRAs has become an established methodology for achieving this goal, from its first practical
74 introduction in 2013-14 (NTP OHAT, 2015; Woodruff and Sutton, 2014), its popularisation in
75 the following few years (Hoffmann et al., 2017; Whaley et al., 2016), and its wider uptake by
76 national and international risk assessment agencies including US EPA (EPA, 2022; EPA,
77 2023), EFSA (EFSA, 2010; EFSA et al., 2017a), and WHO (WHO, 2021).

78 Because SR and CRA methodologies were developed independently of each other, the SR
79 and CRA communities use their own specific terminologies and language. Numerous SRs
80 performed as part of CRAs have shown that these terminologies often are analogous to
81 each other or overlapping, but rarely the same or directly translatable. Also, often a reporting
82 checklist, like the PRISMA checklist, have not been included. It can therefore be difficult to
83 understand which SR method (or to what level/extent) is applied in the CRAs (i.e., whether a
84 given framework or application is sufficiently rigorous to be described as “systematic”) and
85 may be impeding the understanding and therefore potentially slowing the uptake of SR
86 methods in the CRA community.

87 In this project, we will analyse conceptual overlap and differences between the core CRA
88 terms of SR and CRA. This way, we aim to increase the interoperability of SR and CRA
89 terminologies by improving the understanding of the meaning of and the relationships
90 between the core terms of the respective domains.

91 1.1 Project governance

92 This project is a part of the “[Next generation risk assessment in practice](#)” project (VKM,
93 2023) which is included in the European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from
94 Chemicals ([PARC](#); Project 101057014)”. The participants in this project include the
95 members of the research team and the members of the scientific advisory group (SAG). A
96 project group (PG) has been established with the responsibility for drafting the protocol and
97 performing the study.

98 2 Methods

99 2.1 Study design

100 A cross-mapping of core SR and CRA terms will be performed to explore the relationship
101 between the terms and to identify conceptual overlaps. By “core” we mean terms denoting
102 key concepts in the study appraisal, evidence synthesis, and evidence integration steps of
103 systematic reviews. For CRAs and SRs, the scope is limited to methods for quantitative
104 systematic review of health effects of interventions and exposures and methods for evidence
105 synthesis. The project is divided into three phases as shown in Figure 1.

106

107 **Figure 1.** Overview of the three phases and the timeline for the cross-mapping between core
108 systematic review and core chemical risk assessment terms. Abbreviations: CRA, chemical
109 risk assessment; SR, systematic review.

110 The timeline for the project and estimated duration for each phase are shown in Figure 1.
 111 Phase 3 will include weekly one-hour online meetings for the discussion of the descriptions
 112 of SR and CRA term relationships and conceptual overlap, and the anticipated duration of
 113 this phase is 3 to 5 months.

114 2.2 Phase 1: Cataloguing core terms in SR and CRA terminologies

115 The objective is to catalogue core SR and CRA terms that are used for study appraisal,
 116 evidence synthesis and integration.

117 **Creating longlists of SR and CRA terms**

118 A selection of handbooks, guidance documents and glossaries from different sources will be
 119 used to identify core SR and CRA terms (Table 1). Two persons from the PG will
 120 independently go through the documents listed in Table 1 and extract terms that are used for
 121 study appraisal, evidence synthesis or evidence integration. All extracted terms will be
 122 included in the longlist. The longlist of terms will be computed into Excel and will be available
 123 as supplementary materials.

124 It was originally intended that the longlists would be machine generated using the Term
 125 Frequency – Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) method. However, the PG did a pilot
 126 test of the TD-IDF method on the document collection using the English Web corpus
 127 enTenTen21 (Sketch Engine, 2023) as the comparator corpus, and it was [not successful](#)
 128 [found to be less efficient than expected, with challenges on corpus selection, data cleaning,](#)
 129 [and optimisation of term abstraction and rank ordering.](#) ~~Therefore, manually~~ [We have](#)
 130 [therefore determined that manual extraction/identification](#) of ~~the~~ terms will be done instead.

131 **Table 1.** The document collection for identification of core SR and CRA terms.

Document	Reference
SEVCO (Scientific Evidence Code System)	FEVIR Platform Version 0.80.0 (06.12.2022)
Finding What Works in Health Care: Standards for Systematic Reviews	Institute of Medicine Committee on Standards for Systematic Reviews of Comparative Effectiveness (2011)
JBI Manual for Evidence Synthesis	Aromataris et al. (2020)

Application of systematic review methodology to food and feed safety assessments to support decision making	EFSA (2010)
Methodological Expectations of Cochrane Interventions Reviews (MECIR)	Higgins et al. (2023)
Glossary of Terms in The Cochrane Collaboration, Version 4.2.5	(Cochrane Collaboration, 2005)
Handbook for Conducting a Literature Based Health Assessment Using OHAT Approach for Systematic Review and Evidence Integration	NTP OHAT (2019)
Framework for the use of systematic review in chemical risk assessment	WHO (2021)
Guiding Principles and Key Elements for Establishing a Weight of Evidence for Chemical Assessment	OECD (2019)
ORD Staff Handbook for Developing IRIS Assessments	EPA (2022)
Guidance on the assessment of the biological relevance of data in scientific assessments	EFSA et al. (2017b)
PRISMA 2020	(Page et al., 2021)
EFSA glossary	(EFSA, 2024)

132

133 **Creating the final shortlist of core SR and CRA terms**

134 An expert group, consisting of a minimum four experts from the PG and SAG, who have
135 experience within SR, CRA or both fields will be created.

136 The expert group members will individually screen the longlist which contains both CRA and
137 SR terms in Excel. The experts can also add additional terms they believe should be
138 included but are not on the longlist. For each term, the expert group members will rate their
139 level of agreement using a 5-point Likert scale (5 indicates strong agreement, whereas 1

140 indicates strong disagreement) towards two statements: 1) This term is a core CRA term for
141 study appraisal, evidence integration and/or evidence synthesis, 2) This term is a core SR
142 term for study appraisal, evidence integration and/or evidence synthesis.

143 Terms scored “4” or “5” on the Likert scale by one or more members of the expert group will
144 be considered as core terms and included in the shortlist.

145 The shortlists will be presented and discussed in PG and SAG meetings to identify i) terms
146 on the shortlist that are not related to study appraisal, evidence synthesis and integration
147 process, and ii) additional terms that should be included. The final shortlists will be prepared
148 by the PG and be available as supplementary materials. Information on the cumulative score
149 (Likert scale scoring) will also be available.

150 In the case that many core terms are identified and there is a need for prioritisation, the
151 cumulative scores (Likert scale) will be used to prioritise terms to be included in the cross-
152 mapping.

153 2.3 Phase 2: Preparing a list of existing definitions of SR and CRA terms

154 The objective of this phase is to prepare a list of a representative range of definitions of the
155 core SR and CRA terms.

156 The definitions for the SR and CRA terms will be primarily collected from glossaries,
157 guidance’s and handbooks listed in Table 1. However, if the definitions are not listed in those
158 documents other sources might be used, which will be identified by an Internet search or
159 brainstorming within the PG and SAG. The definitions of the core SR and CRA terms will be
160 extracted by one PG member and checked by another PG member. Each extracted
161 definition will be tagged with from which source it was extracted from. The table will be made
162 available as supplementary materials.

163 2.5 Phase 3: Identifying conceptual overlap between CRA and SR terms

164 The objective is to identify areas of conceptual overlap and difference between CRA terms
165 and SR terms. The cross-mapping will be done via a consensus process involving an expert
166 group with PG and SAG members and additional experts (see section 2.6) self-identifying as
167 having relevant CRA and/or SR expertise. The main steps in the cross-mapping are shown
168 in Table 2. A more detailed overview of the steps is included in the Supplementary materials
169 (Table S-1). The approach is adapted from the consensus process used in the development
170 of the SEVCO methods ontology and the GRADE Ontology. (Alper et al., 2024; Alper et al.,
171 2021).

172 **Table 2.** The four main steps in the cross-mapping process.

Step	What
<p>1. Identification of relationships between core CRA terms and core SR terms.</p>	<p>PG will map which terms are related.</p>
<p>2. Assembling an expert group with PG members, SAG members, and additional experts, all self-identifying as having relevant SR and/or CRA expertise.</p>	<p>The relationship between terms is discussed in the expert group. Descriptions of the relationships between the terms will be drafted according to the discussion.</p>
<p>3. Identification of agreement on discussed descriptions (approval of the draft statements from step 2).</p>	<p>The experts vote (anonymously, online) “agree” or “not agree” on approval of the draft statement from step 2.</p> <p>The criteria for agreement are: i) at least 5 members voted AND ii) all votes were for “agree”.</p> <p>If an agreement is reached, stop here.</p> <p>If no agreement is reached, proceed to step 4.</p>
<p>4. Suggestion of changes to the descriptions where no agreement was reached.</p>	<p>The result of the vote is discussed in the expert group and redrafted when needed. Participants will vote (online) “agree” or “not agree” on each discussed statement. The criteria for agreement for descriptions of relationships between the terms that are discussed for the second time are: i) at least 5 members voted AND ii) at least 80% of the votes were for “agree”.</p> <p>If an agreement is reached, stop here.</p> <p>If no agreement is reached, proceed to step 3.</p>

	Steps 3 and 4 are repeated a maximum of two times. If agreement is not reached, no statement of the relationship between the CRA and the SR terms will be created. However, information on the difficulties and suggested descriptions will be included as supplementary materials
--	--

173

174 **2.6 The expert groups participating in phase 3**

175 The experts participating in the online meetings will be PG and SAG members and additional
176 experts self-identifying as having relevant SR or CRA expertise. Recruitment of the
177 additional experts will be done by PG and SAG members via their national and international
178 SR and CRA networks. Anyone self-identifying as having the relevant expertise can sign up
179 at any time. Expert group participants will be sent project updates, in particular notifications
180 of when terms are open for vote, by email. Votes will be cast by email to the PG member
181 tasked with facilitating the discussion and voting process. The facilitator will anonymise the
182 votes to the rest of the PG and expert group.

183 Following the additional experts first participation, they will be asked to fill out a short
184 questionnaire with questions about their affiliation, type of profession, country of residence,
185 gender, age, and number of years of experience with SRs and CRAs (phase 3). Information
186 on race or ethnicity will not be collected because in Norway this information falls under the
187 category of “sensitive personal data” and on a general note this type of data is not legal to be
188 collected or handled.

189

190 Everyone on the mailing list will receive meeting documents in front of the meetings.
191 Everyone that participated in a meeting will be asked to participate in the voting after the
192 meeting. The votes will not be anonymous for the PG but will be anonymised in the
193 manuscript.

194 Expert Group members are eligible to be co-authors if they i) vote and/or comment on at
195 least ten terms or cross-mappings in total, and ii) reviews the manuscript. Expert group
196 members not eligible to be co-authors will be listed in the acknowledgements. No financial
197 compensation or other incentives are offered for the participation as additional expert.

198 3 Anticipated results

199 In this section we describe how the result of the study will be presented in the results section
200 of the finalised manuscript. All other results will be made available as supplementary
201 materials.

202 3.1 Core SR and CRA terms

203 A list of core terms in the SR and CRA terminologies, and the Likert scale scoring, will be
204 presented. A table illustrating a proposed way to present the results is included in the
205 Supplementary materials (Table S-2).

206 3.2 SR and CRA term definitions

207 The definitions of SR and CRA core terms and their synonyms will be presented. Tables
208 illustrating the presentation of the catalogued definitions of SR and CRA terms are included
209 in the Supplementary materials (Tables S-3 and S-4). The presentation of participant
210 characteristics for the expert group participating in phase 3 is illustrated in the
211 Supplementary materials (Table S-6).

212 3.4 Conceptual overlap between core SR and core CRA terms

213 Descriptions of the relationship between CRA terms and SR terms will be presented. Tables
214 illustrating how this information will be presented are included in the Supplementary
215 materials. The proposed presentation of the cross-mapping of CRA terms on the SR terms is
216 shown in the Supplementary materials (Table S-5). The proposed presentation of the SR
217 terms and the related CRA terms and the conceptual overlap is shown in the Supplementary
218 materials (Table S-6). The proposed presentation of participant characteristics for the expert
219 group participating in phase 3 is shown in the Supplementary materials (Table S-7).

220 4 Limitations

221 The methods described in this protocol are considered to provide a grounded process
222 towards a common understanding for the meaning of these terms without being too time-
223 consuming. A consequence may be that not all relevant terms from all SR and CRA
224 communities will be included.

225 While we attempt to involve a broad and diverse group of experts from several institutions in
226 this project, it is possible that we will not be able to recruit participants from all relevant
227 institutions within the SR and CRA communities. However, being able to distribute
228 information through the networks of both the PG and the SAG, we expect to recruit
229 participants from several relevant institutions.

230 For the online group discussions in Phase 3, there is a risk for some persons to dominate
231 the discussion. To reduce this, an experienced and neutral moderator (PW) will facilitate the
232 discussions. Anonymous voting online should also allow for more ease at disagreeing with
233 strong personalities and participants assumed higher in a social hierarchy. Because we are
234 aiming at a high level of consensus, voting will give all participants the opportunity to
235 contribute over several rounds of development of the cross-map, with the requirement that
236 their comments are considered in each round of discussion. If any participants feel their
237 comments are not responded to, they can vote “no” in the next round of voting. Also, we are
238 planning for a diverse mix of experiences and backgrounds in the group.

239 Dissemination

240 The outcome of this project will be published in a scientific journal.

241 Abbreviations

242 CRA: chemical risk assessment

243 PG: project group

244 SAG: scientific advisory group

245 SEVCO: Scientific Evidence Code System

246 SR: systematic review

247 Definition

248 **Core terms** are in this project defined as terms denoting key concepts in the study
249 appraisal, evidence synthesis, and evidence integration steps of systematic reviews.

250 Funding

251 Camilla Svendsen, Gro H. Mathisen, Gunn E. Vist, Trine Husøy, Heather M.R. Ames, Emma
252 Di Consiglio, Kyriaki Machera, Eliana Spilioti, Anastasia Spyropoulou, Olga
253 Tcheremenskaia, Emanuela Testai, and Paul Whaley were supported by HORIZON-HLTH-
254 2021-ENVHLTH-03, Grant [101057014]; Nicolas Roth was supported by The Swiss State
255 Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) under contract no. 22.00230.

256 Ethical considerations

257 Application for ethical approval will be submitted to the Norwegian Institute of Public Health.

258 Declaration of interests

259 Completed declaration of interest forms for each author are available as supplementary
260 materials. The authors declare no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research,
261 authorship, and/or publication of this protocol.

262 Authors contribution

263 **Conceptualization:** Camilla Svendsen, Gro H. Mathisen, Gunn E. Vist, Trine Husøy, and
264 Paul Whaley.

265 **Funding acquisition:** Camilla Svendsen and Gro H. Mathisen.

266 **Methodology:** Camilla Svendsen, Gro H. Mathisen, and Paul Whaley.

267 **Project administration:** Camilla Svendsen and Gro H. Mathisen.

268 **Supervision:** Paul Whaley.

269 **Visualization:** Camilla Svendsen, Gro H. Mathisen, and Paul Whaley.

270 **Writing - original draft:** Camilla Svendsen, Gro H. Mathisen, Gunn E. Vist, and Paul
271 Whaley.

272 **Writing - review & editing:** Camilla Svendsen, Gro H. Mathisen, Gunn E. Vist, Trine Husøy,
273 Heather M. Ames, Anna Beronius, Emma Di Consiglio, Ingrid Druwe, Thomas Hartung,
274 Sebastian Hoffmann, Carlijn R. Hooijmans, Kyriaki Machera, Joshua F. Robinson, Erwin
275 Roggen, Andrew A. Rooney, Nicolas Roth, Eliana Spilioti, Anastasia Spyropoulou, Olga
276 Tcheremenskaia, Emanuela Testai, Mathieu Vinken, and Paul Whaley.

277 References

278 Alper B., Dehnbostel J., Whaley P., Group G.O.P. (2024) Protocol for development of the
279 GRADE Ontology. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11002448>.

280 Alper B.S., Dehnbostel J., Lehmann H., Whaley P., Wilkins K.J., Tufte J., Yurk R.A., Ojha N.,
281 Afzal M. (2021) For the COVID-19 Knowledge Accelerator (COKA) Initiative.

282 Scientific Evidence Code System Development Protocol. Created November 16,
283 2021. Last revised December 8, 2021. Available at:

284 [https://docs.google.com/document/d/1pzGLdyVCKcu3s2gfSfPpXDQLIQsFnLZR14ld](https://docs.google.com/document/d/1pzGLdyVCKcu3s2gfSfPpXDQLIQsFnLZR14ldw0nD1g0)
285 [w0nD1g0](https://docs.google.com/document/d/1pzGLdyVCKcu3s2gfSfPpXDQLIQsFnLZR14ldw0nD1g0).

286 Aromataris E., Munn Z., (Editors). (2020) JBI Manual for Evidence Synthesis. JBI, 2020.

287 Available from <https://synthesismanual.jbi.global>. [https://doi.org/10.46658/JBIMES-](https://doi.org/10.46658/JBIMES-20-01)
288 [20-01](https://doi.org/10.46658/JBIMES-20-01). , <https://jbi-global->

289 [wiki.refined.site/space/MANUAL/4685874/Downloadable+PDF+-](https://wiki.refined.site/space/MANUAL/4685874/Downloadable+PDF+-+current+version?attachment=/rest/api/content/4685874/child/attachment/att4691824/download&type=application/pdf&filename=JBIMES_2021April)
290 [+current+version?attachment=/rest/api/content/4685874/child/attachment/att4691824](https://wiki.refined.site/space/MANUAL/4685874/Downloadable+PDF+-+current+version?attachment=/rest/api/content/4685874/child/attachment/att4691824/download&type=application/pdf&filename=JBIMES_2021April)
291 [/download&type=application/pdf&filename=JBIMES_2021April.](https://wiki.refined.site/space/MANUAL/4685874/Downloadable+PDF+-+current+version?attachment=/rest/api/content/4685874/child/attachment/att4691824/download&type=application/pdf&filename=JBIMES_2021April)

292 Cochrane Collaboration. (2005) Glossary of Terms in The Cochrane Collaboration, Version
293 4.2.5 <http://aaz.hr/resources/pages/57/7.%20Cochrane%20glossary.pdf>.

294 EFSA. (2010) Application of systematic review methodology to food and feed safety
295 assessments to support decision making. EFSA Journal 8:1637. DOI:
296 <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2010.1637>.

297 EFSA. (2024) Glossary, European Food Safety Authority,
298 <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/glossary-taxonomy-terms>.

299 EFSA, Hardy A., Benford D., Halldorsson T., Jeger M.J., Knutsen H.K., More S., Naegeli H.,
300 Noteborn H., Ockleford C., Ricci A., Rychen G., Schlatter J.R., Silano V., Solecki R.,
301 Turck D., Benfenati E., Chaudhry Q.M., Craig P., Frampton G., Greiner M., Hart A.,
302 Hogstrand C., Lambre C., Luttik R., Makowski D., Siani A., Wahlstroem H., Aguilera
303 J., Dorne J.-L., Fernandez Dumont A., Hempen M., Valtueña M., Martino L., Smeraldi
304 C., Terron A., Georgiadis N., Younes M. (2017a) Guidance on the use of the weight
305 of evidence approach in scientific assessments. EFSA Journal 15:e04971. DOI:
306 10.2903/j.efsa.2017.4971.

307 EFSA, Hardy A., Benford D., Halldorsson T., Jeger M.J., Knutsen H.K., More S., Naegeli H.,
308 Noteborn H., Ockleford C., Ricci A., Rychen G., Schlatter J.R., Silano V., Solecki R.,
309 Turck D., Younes M., Bresson J.-L., Griffin J., Benekou S.H., van Loveren H., Luttik
310 R., Messean A., Penninks A., Ru G., Stegeman J.A., van der Werf W., Westendorf
311 J., Woutersen R.A., Barizzone F., Bottex B., Lanzoni A., Georgiadis N., Alexander J.
312 (2017b) Guidance on the assessment of the biological relevance of data in scientific
313 assessments. EFSA Journal 15:e04970. DOI: 10.2903/j.efsa.2017.4970.

314 EPA. (2022) ORD Staff Handbook for Developing IRIS Assessments. U.S. EPA Office of
315 Research and Development, Washington, DC, EPA/600/R-22/268,
316 https://ordspub.epa.gov/ords/eims/eimscomm.getfile?p_download_id=545991.

317 EPA. (2023) Draft Protocol for Systematic Review in TSCA Risk Evaluations (assessed
318 10.02.2023), United States Environmental Protection Agency,
319 [https://www.epa.gov/assessing-and-managing-chemicals-under-tsca/draft-protocol-](https://www.epa.gov/assessing-and-managing-chemicals-under-tsca/draft-protocol-systematic-review-tsca-risk-evaluations)
320 [systematic-review-tsca-risk-evaluations](https://www.epa.gov/assessing-and-managing-chemicals-under-tsca/draft-protocol-systematic-review-tsca-risk-evaluations).

321 FEvIR Platform Version 0.80.0. (06.12.2022) Scientific Evidence Code System (SEVCO).
322 Computable Publishing®: CodeSystem Viewer,
323 <https://fevir.net/resources/CodeSystem/27270#SEVCO:00001>.

324 Higgins J., Lasserso T., Thomas J., Flemyng E., Churchill R. (2023) Standards for the
325 conduct of new Cochrane Intervention Reviews, and the planning and conduct of

326 updates. Methodological Expectations of Cochrane Intervention Reviews (MECIR).
327 MECIR Manual (Version August 2023) Cochrane Community,
328 https://community.cochrane.org/book_pdf/545.

329 Hoffmann S., de Vries R.B.M., Stephens M.L., Beck N.B., Dirven H.A.A.M., Fowle J.R.,
330 Goodman J.E., Hartung T., Kimber I., Lalu M.M., Thayer K., Whaley P., Wikoff D.,
331 Tsaion K. (2017) A primer on systematic reviews in toxicology. Archives of
332 Toxicology 91:2551-2575. DOI: 10.1007/s00204-017-1980-3.

333 Institute of Medicine Committee on Standards for Systematic Reviews of Comparative
334 Effectiveness R. (2011), in: J. Eden, et al. (Eds.), Finding What Works in Health
335 Care: Standards for Systematic Reviews, National Academies Press (US) Copyright
336 2011 by the National Academy of Sciences. All rights reserved., Washington (DC).

337 NTP OHAT. (2015) OHAT Risk of Bias Rating Tool for Human and Animal Studies, Office of
338 Health Assessment and Translation (OHAT), Division of the National Toxicology
339 Program, National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences,
340 https://ntp.niehs.nih.gov/ntp/ohat/pubs/riskofbiastool_508.pdf.

341 NTP OHAT. (2019) Handbook for Conducting a Literature Based Health Assessment Using
342 OHAT Approach for Systematic Review and Evidence Integration, Office of Health
343 Assessment and Translation (OHAT), Division of the National Toxicology Program,
344 National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences,
345 https://ntp.niehs.nih.gov/ntp/ohat/pubs/handbookmarch2019_508.pdf.

346 OECD. (2019) Guiding Principles and Key Elements for Establishing a Weight of Evidence
347 for Chemical Assessment, Series on Testing and Assessment No. 311, Environment,
348 Health and Safety Division, Environment Directorate, The Organisation for Economic
349 Co-operation and Development, [https://www.oecd.org/chemicalsafety/risk-](https://www.oecd.org/chemicalsafety/risk-assessment/guiding-principles-and-key-elements-for-establishing-a-weight-of-evidence-for-chemical-assessment.pdf)
350 [assessment/guiding-principles-and-key-elements-for-establishing-a-weight-of-](https://www.oecd.org/chemicalsafety/risk-assessment/guiding-principles-and-key-elements-for-establishing-a-weight-of-evidence-for-chemical-assessment.pdf)
351 [evidence-for-chemical-assessment.pdf](https://www.oecd.org/chemicalsafety/risk-assessment/guiding-principles-and-key-elements-for-establishing-a-weight-of-evidence-for-chemical-assessment.pdf).

352 Page M.J., McKenzie J.E., Bossuyt P.M., Boutron I., Hoffmann T.C., Mulrow C.D., Shamseer
353 L., Tetzlaff J.M., Akl E.A., Brennan S.E., Chou R., Glanville J., Grimshaw J.M.,
354 Hróbjartsson A., Lalu M.M., Li T., Loder E.W., Mayo-Wilson E., McDonald S.,
355 McGuinness L.A., Stewart L.A., Thomas J., Tricco A.C., Welch V.A., Whiting P.,
356 Moher D. (2021) The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting
357 systematic reviews. Bmj 372:n71. DOI: 10.1136/bmj.n71.

358 Sketch Engine. (2023) enTenTen: Corpus of the English Web,
359 <https://www.sketchengine.eu/ententen-english-corpus/>.

360 VKM. (2023) The Norwegian Scientific Committee of Food and Environment (VKM)
361 participates in the European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals
362 (PARC) (assessed 11.05.2023),

363 [https://vkm.no/english/parc/parceuropeanpartnershipfortheassessmentofrisksfromche](https://vkm.no/english/parc/parceuropeanpartnershipfortheassessmentofrisksfromchemicals.4.7205492a1864a8c8da2dcfd9.html)
364 [micals.4.7205492a1864a8c8da2dcfd9.html](https://vkm.no/english/parc/parceuropeanpartnershipfortheassessmentofrisksfromchemicals.4.7205492a1864a8c8da2dcfd9.html).

365 Whaley P., Halsall C., Ågerstrand M., Aiassa E., Benford D., Bilotta G., Coggon D., Collins
366 C., Dempsey C., Duarte-Davidson R., FitzGerald R., Galay-Burgos M., Gee D.,
367 Hoffmann S., Lam J., Lasserson T., Levy L., Lipworth S., Ross S.M., Martin O.,
368 Meads C., Meyer-Baron M., Miller J., Pease C., Rooney A., Sapiets A., Stewart G.,
369 Taylor D. (2016) Implementing systematic review techniques in chemical risk
370 assessment: Challenges, opportunities and recommendations. *Environ Int* 92-
371 93:556-64. DOI: 10.1016/j.envint.2015.11.002.

372 WHO. (2021) Framework for the use of systematic review in chemical risk assessment.
373 Geneva: World Health Organization. Licence: CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 IGO,
374 <https://apps.who.int/iris/rest/bitstreams/1387316/retrieve>.

375 Woodruff T.J., Sutton P. (2014) The Navigation Guide systematic review methodology: a
376 rigorous and transparent method for translating environmental health science into
377 better health outcomes. *Environ Health Perspect* 122:1007-14. DOI:
378 10.1289/ehp.1307175.

379